

A REVIEW PAPER ON THE HOTEL INDUSTRY – A STUDY OF RECENT TRENDS AFTER COVID-19 IN THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY IN GUJARAT

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ABSTRACT:

It is very necessary to be updated with market trends nowadays. Especially for every company, because they have a common purpose: maximization of profit. Technology is changing rapidly, and the choice of customers and their selection criteria are not fixed due to advanced features and multiple options available. Even after the Covid-19 pandemic, the hotel industry has implemented so many changes for safety purposes and it becomes a kind of new trend. Customers are expecting some safety precautions when they visit any hotel.

This research paper is prepared to find out the recent trends in the hotel industry in terms of safety purposes and market requirements as well. We have collected the primary data by approaching various hotels, having a conversation with the staff, and also some secondary data from the earlier research paper, websites, and blogs. The secondary data has provided information regarding the change in trend in past years and its effect on the industry.

We will come to know about what kind of latest trends are there in the hotel industry, especially after Covid-19, the expectations of the customers from the management, and efforts done by the management to satisfy the requirement of the customers in Gujarat.

KEYWORDS:

HOTEL INDUSTRY, RECENT TRENDS, COVID-19, INNOVATIONS.

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INTRODUCTION

From last one decade, we are the victim of drastic change in the market due to new advanced technologies. Digitalization, innovative software, applications, social media, and the internet all these things have comprised the entire market everywhere. People have to adopt new technology through some of the actions taken by the Government of India. Just like demonetization in 2016. After that people are having such monetary transactions by UPI method only. After that in 2020, the Covid-19 pandemic arrived and the entire world has been affected. So, people came to know about the importance of google meet, zoom applications by which they can not only communicate with each other but also do their office work. These things were already there even before demonetization and covid, but the usage has increased after these noticeable changes in the country. Initially, it was difficult to cop-up with this new trend but slowly it becomes a part of a routine. Nowadays, majority of the

people are using digital apps, online classes, online bookings, online reviews of institutes, etc. So they can decide on the further plan.

The hotel industry is also affected by this technological trend and the management of the institutions is following the new tendency required by the new scenario. The hotel management is following covid guidelines such as hand sanitizer, employees are providing service by wearing masks, and some hygienic precautionary safety measurement has been taken care of also. Also, they have taken advantage of online booking on *make my trip*, *goibobo*, *trivago*, *yatra*, etc. People are going through the review of the customers before the visit to the venue. So, hotel management tries to have positive feedback from the customers so they can have more in the future. So many hotels have their individual accounts on Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, etc. They regularly post new updates regarding their activities. So that they can attract new

customers. Because today is the era of social media and if anyone wants to increase publicity, they always prefer to have a social media account. This is also one of the trends which can increase the business of the institution.

NEED

The main aim of this research is to find out the changes that has been implemented by hotel management as per the market trend. Everyone wants some change but not every time change needs to be accepted by everyone. So, whether people have positive feedback or negative is to be found. So, every time is not necessary that innovation that is implemented by hotel management is accepted by the customers.

This research paper will provide you with some other details also, like how frequently the customers visit any hotel. How do they choose to visit a particular hotel and what are the liking factors according to the recent trend? This research paper will be beneficial to hotel management because they can be aware of some of the trends of which they are not having an idea.

Apart from the technical aspect, what kind of additional facilities can be facilitated by the hotel management like valet parking, spa, laundry, pick up and drop facilities from the airport, and any other places? Sometimes customers are not willing to visit the hotel because of the non-availability of this kind of facility. By executing this research paper, we can come to know about the preferences of the customers in terms of non-technical advantages.

OBJECTIVES:

- To study the recent market trend in the hospitality industry in Gujarat Region
- To study the influence on the customers by giving additional facilities from the hotel management to compete in the market
- To examine various factors of the selection criteria, technical i.e. internet base, and non-technical, according to the trend

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Atul Sheel (2004) – It was very early stage research in the hospitality industry. Research has been done at the University of Massachusetts, Amherst. As per the author, *“the blocked dollar and consequential added purchasing power for distant tourists could also mean more foreign travel and international travel money for U.S. hospitality and tourism businesses. If this turns out to be the case, the approaching era would not be really “unbiased” for the hospitality industry after all!* There was an assumption that if there would be no terrorist attacks, war-related activity, or tsunamis, it is expected that demand for US hotel rooms should increase further. - ¹

Manal Bannaciri (2012) – *“The findings of this study suggest that blogs have a potentially negative impact on the perceptions, even when statements are positive.* By having such information on the blog, customers decide whether to

visit any hotel or not. And found that customers have more trust in the information which is available on the website of the hotel. Then mixed blogs and after the positive blog available on the internet. In the statistical data, the hotel website scored the most for the selection criteria of the customers.” - ²

Mr. sc. Lvica Batinic (2013) – *“New requirements, demands, and wants of clients have led to the appearance of new trends in hospitality offerings strategy.* Wellness and spa hotels, boutique hotels, all-inclusive hotels, and wine and lounge bars are only some of the main trends and successful hospitality managers will create politics of development in accordance with new requirements and the needs of the global market.” - ³

P. A. Anawade & Dr. Shilpa K. Bendale (2016) – *“Garden hotels concept, improving the number of beds, focus on 4 lanes, use and focus on airport facility, etc. are the most common trend in the hotel industry.* As per the conclusion of the research paper, trends are changing constantly day by day. Some of the changes are derived from the monetary condition of the individual. The owner of the hotels has to keep their eye open to look outside the world for the current trend so they can modify themselves accordingly.” - ⁴

Nana Akhalia & Manana Vasadze (2016) – The research was made in Georgia. And according to the authors, *“Development of hotel industry is very important in that country for socio-economic development.* Though it was unknown to tourists, the development of hotels became a very positive factor and they expected high standards for the customers.” - ⁵

Gaurav Purohit & Divya Purohit (2016) – *“The hospitality industry rests on the perception of bringing the best facility possible to the client and if they don't succeed to attempt, there can be serious implications because most of the market players have risen above the concept of satisfaction and are adamant in delivering services that may surprise the guest and bring about a feeling that he may live up with for a longer period.”* - ⁶

Inder Singh (2019) – *“As per the conclusion of the research paper – Social gatherings on the internet have impacted a lot on hotel industry nowadays. The criticism which is given in the feedback from the customer reduces the credibility of the hotel.* And people use social media when there are so many options available for them when they want to visit any hotel outside. If a hotel can provide good service then customers will give more stars and positive reviews which the company can increase productivity.” - ⁷

Dr. Atul Ramgade & Prof. Shobha Kshirsagar (2019) – *“Focus on the information system has been mentioned in this research paper.* According to the author – hotel management should arrange such kind of training for their employees so that they can facilitate the customers as and when they required technical assistance. The adoption of new automation techniques can sustain the market competition.” - ⁸

Lerzan Aksoy, Sunmee Choi, Tarik Dogru, Timothy

Keiningham, Melanie Lorenz, Dan Rubin, J. Bruce Tracey (2022) – This research paper has taken place just after Covid – 19. As the authors – “Cov (Sheel 2004) (Bennaciri 2012) (Batinic 2013)id has pushed safety, and disease prevention issues to the forefront in the short term. But even in the long term, this issue’s importance will be increased from a safety point of view.” - 9

RESEARCH TOOLS:

SAMPLE SIZE:

In this research paper, contact has been done with nineteen hotels in different cities and get information regarding the vision of hotel management as well as customers, their feedback, and opinion regarding recent trends in the hotel industry in the Gujarat region, especially after Covid-19. The majority of the research has been prepared as per the primary data. So, a true and fair view can be obtained for the concerned topic. The data has been analysed 360 degrees and concluded the accurate result.

FINDINGS: - (RESPONDENT RELATED INFORMATION)

After the analysis of primary data and secondary data, we have generated some of the following charts as per the various criteria which are mentioned below:

HOTEL CATEGORY:

Sr. No.	Category	Number of Samples	In Percentage
1	3 Star Hotels	7	36.85%
2	4 Star Hotels	4	21.06%
3	5 Star Hotels	2	10.52%
4	Not Applicable	6	31.57%
	Total	19	100%

Total 19 hotels has been taken for the sampling purpose. All the hotel are having different category like 5 star, 4 star, 3 star and not applicable in this category. As we study the table, more than 36% of the hotels are coming under the 3-star category, 21% are 4-star, 11% from 5-star, and 32% of the hotels don’t have any star category. All have sustained very crucially during the Covid-19 pandemic and now they are back to the market with different development as per the customers’ requirements.

AVAILABILITY OF ROOMS:

Sr. No.	Particular	Number
1	1 to 20	5
2	21 to 40	7

3	41 to 60	6
4	More than 60	1
	Total	19

Only 1, 5 star hotel is having more than 60 rooms and the rest of the hotels have less than that. Training and guidance are providing to the employees for the proper maintenance of the hotel. Because cleanliness is the first necessary criterion for safety purposes. Although, they have a variety of rooms available like the deluxe, executive, suit, etc. The rate of the room defers according to the category because it provides economic relief to the customers and gives various facilities accordingly.

ONLINE HOTEL BOOKING FACILITY:

Sr. No.	Particular	Number
1	Yes	14
2	No	05
	Total	19

Only booking is widely used by customers. Because before leaving the residence, customers want to confirm their bookings so they can travel comfortably. 14 hotels are

providing online facilities either through their own website or from others like make my trip, goibobo, yatra, etc. Apart from online booking, they are providing a spa, valet parking, gym, etc. for the remaining interest of the customers.

OVERALL CUSTOMERS FEEDBACK AS PER THE FEEDBACK FORM:

Sr. No.	Category	No. of Customers	In Percentage
1	Excellent	56	31.11%
2	Very Good	72	40.00%
3	Good	35	19.44%
4	Average	13	7.22%
5	Poor	4	2.22%
	Total	180	100.00%

Hotels are taking feedback from the customers also and customers are giving their feedback according to their experience. Here, 40% of the customers has given a "Very Good" rank while in the next place "Excellent" with more than 31% vote from the customers. So, we can say that almost 71% of the customers are satisfied with the service and system of the hotel management. That 17% (13% + 4%) need to serve better so they can recommend other friends or family to visit that hotel again.

SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNT AVAILABILITY:

Sr. No.	Particular	Number
1	Yes	16
2	No	03
	Total	19

Having marketing on social media is very essential in today's era. Everyone has their own social media account and people are utilizing most of their time on social media. In this scenario, having a social media account of the hotel itself is a big opportunity to grab customers. In our sample research, 16 hotels out of 19 have social media accounts and they have regularly updated profiles by posting recent events, innovations, and development. It creates a very good impact on the credibility and trustworthiness of the hotels.

CONCLUSION

After the collection of primary as well as secondary data, we have come to the conclusion that there has been drastic changes took place as development in the hotel industry. Almost all the hotels are following the covid-19 guidelines and trying to attract customers by implementing innovations so more and more information is spreading to increase the positive image. Yet, as per the review of the hotel management, they have to be ready forever for new development and technological changes. Because the market is changing rapidly and companies are bound to satisfy the expectations of the customers and this will lead them to remain constant in the market for a longer period of time.

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